

THE EFFECT OF MATRIX SHEAR DEFORMATION AND CRACKING ON THE TOUGHNESS OF BORON/ALUMINUM

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In linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) the influence of a plastic zone at the crack tip is widely known. The LEFM is applicable, when the size of the plastic zone is small compared with crack and specimen dimensions. In this case the crack length is corrected considering the length of the plastic zone.

Application of LEFM to composite materials with elastic stiff fibers in a ductile matrix gives rise to the question of the influence of the plastic zone. The shape and the size of the plastic zone, occurring only in the ductile matrix is dependent on the orientation of the constituent layers. In unidirectional B/Al with a crack perpendicular to the fibers and the load in fiber direction there is a plastic (shear) zone at the crack tip, which extends mainly in the fiber direction.

The present investigation on double edge notched (DEN) specimens cut out of unidirectional B/Al shows that at increasing notch length $a = 2.5-18.5$ mm, with the ratio notch length/width being constant ($2 a/W = 0.5$), shear deformation can become so severe that at the notch tip shear cracking occurs parallel to the fibers. It is found that with this increasing notch length the fracture toughness increases. The increase in toughness, which is stronger than that, following from the point stress criterion, can only partly be explained by the formation of shear cracks at the notch tip. This is revealed by tests on specimens where the toughness has been determined as a function of the shear crack length. These shear cracks are made artificially by applying cyclic loading on the DEN specimens, before the fracture test is performed.

Strain distribution measurements at the notch tip indicate that the rising toughness also results from lagging tensile stresses on a few fiber distances from the notch tip. This phenomenon was examined at the largest investigated notch ($a = 18.5$ mm).

Although in the investigated angle plies $90/0/90/0/90$ and $(+45/0/-45)$, the extension of a plastic zone is smaller and no extensive matrix cracking occurs, the toughness rises again with increasing crack length.

1. INTRODUCTION

In LEFM the stress distribution at the crack tip is governed by the stress intensity factor K , which reaches a critical value, e.g. K_0 , K_Q , K_{IC} at the beginning of crack extension, a certain amount of crack extension or fracture under plane strain conditions, respectively. The toughness K_0 , which is the principal subject of

the present investigation, follows from

$$K_0 = \sigma_0 Y \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (1)$$

where σ_0 : stress at the beginning of crack extension
 a^0 : crack length on either specimen side (DEN specimens)
 Y : finite width correction factor.

The toughness has a practical value when it is independent of the crack length. However, in a number of investigations on boron/aluminum [1-3] a rising toughness K_{\max} (at specimen fracture) was found with an increasing notch length. This phenomenon is not restricted to composites. Thin sheets of conventional materials show the same effect [4]. The toughness at the beginning of crack extension K_0 is for conventional materials almost independent of the crack length [5], a fact which could not be confirmed for unidirectional B/AI [3].

Whitney and Nuismer [6] developed other fracture criterions, namely the point and average stress criterion which seem to describe fracture better. According to these models, fracture occurs when the stress at the crack tip over a characteristic length d_0 is higher (point-stress criterion: P.S.C.) or when the average stress over a fixed characteristic length a_0 is equal to the unnotched tensile strength σ_U (average stress criterion: A.S.C.). These characteristic lengths d_0 and a_0 should be material constants, when these criterions are of practical importance. In fact they were able to explain a rising toughness with increasing notch length starting from the stress at a distance r from the notch tip or at a distance x ($= a+r$) from the (DEN) specimen side

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{Y\sigma x}{\sqrt{x^2 - a^2}} \quad x > a \quad (2)$$

with σ : applied stress

which they developed as a limit case from Lekhnitskii's [7] solution for an elliptical cavity in an infinite anisotropic plate. The stress distribution at the crack tip according to the LEFM is given by

$$\sigma(r) = Y \sigma \sqrt{a/2r} \quad (3)$$

which is a limit of Eq. (2) when the crack length a becomes very large.

The toughness at the beginning of crack extension according to the point and average stress criterion follows from

$$K_0 \text{ (P.S.C.)} = \sigma_U \sqrt{\pi a (1 - \epsilon_1^2)} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{with } \epsilon_1 = \frac{a}{a+d_0}$$

for the point stress criterion and

$$K_0 \text{ (A.S.C.)} = \sigma_U \sqrt{\pi a} \cdot \epsilon_2 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{with } \epsilon_2 = \frac{a}{2a+a_0}$$

for the average stress criterion. Eq. (4) and (5) show that for a small crack length $K_0 \rightarrow 0$, whereas for a large crack length the toughness approaches $K_0 \text{ (P.S.C.)} = \sigma_U \sqrt{2\pi d_0}$ for the point stress criterion and $K_0 \text{ (A.S.C.)} = \sigma_U \sqrt{\pi a_0}/2$ for the average stress criterion, respectively.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

Materials with two different fibers were investigated as indicated in Table 1.

Fiber	ϕ μm	Matrix	Bonding Process $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{bar}/\text{min}$	Laminate Orientation	Fiber Volume %	UTS σ_{u2} N/mm^2
B-SiC	147	6061 Foil 4343 Plasma Spray	600/10/10	$(0)_5$	54	1069
B-B ₄ C	104	6061 Foil 6061 Plasma Spray	610/48/30	90/0/90/0/90 (+45/0/-45) _s	45 44	559 493

Table 1. The investigated materials

The B-SiC/Al material was produced by MBB, Munich, whereas the B-B₄C/Al angle plies were fabricated at the DFVLR, Stuttgart.

Specimens were cut out of the plates with a diamant wheel; those to be used for the determination of the tensile strength had a width of 10 mm and those for fracture mechanics tests had a width of 10 to 74 mm for the unidirectional and 20-40 mm for the investigated angle plies. The fracture mechanics tests were conducted on specimens with edge notches (DEN), which had again been produced with a diamant wheel. The notch root radius was 0.15-0.2 mm. In all cases the relative notch length was $2a/W = 0.5$. By electron discharge machining a contour was made on both sides of the specimens, which allowed the crack opening displacement (COD) to be measured with a clip gage during the test. The specimen length between the grips L to the width W was kept constant at $L/W = 6$ for all DEN specimens.

On some of the specimens the deformation at the notch tip was studied by a moire technique using mismatch. A grid with 1000 points/25.4 mm was glued on the specimen. In contact with a mastergrille (33,3 lines/mm) the grid produces fringes, perpendicular to the loading direction with a pitch of 0.164 mm. A displacement on the specimen surface of a point-pitch causes in the moire pattern a displacement over a fringe-pitch. The gain is small (fringe pitch/grid pitch = 6.3) but the displacement can be examined on a relatively large surface. The moire displacement pattern near the crack tip is registered photographically to examine later form and size of the deformation zone.

Finally, on two DEN specimens out of the unidirectional B-SiC/Al ($W = 20$ and 74 mm) the strain distribution at the notch tip was measured with a strain gage chain.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The Toughness K_0 in Dependency on the Notch Length

Crack extension is detectable through a sudden COD increase in the load-COD curve (Fig. 1), which is registered during the test for both notches. A sudden COD increase of 1 and 2 μm for the angle plies and unidirectional material, respectively, was taken as the criterion for crack extension. These COD steps represent a crack extension of 0.5-1 fiber distance, as can be determined from the stress-COD curves (e.g. Fig. 1). The beginning of crack extension at the side notches usually takes place at a different load. For this reason the load at the beginning of crack extension was determined for every notch. With the average load the stress at crack extension σ_0 was calculated.

The toughness at the beginning of crack extension K_0 was estimated with Eq. (1) by substituting the stress σ_0 , the notch length a and the isotropic finite width correction factor. The finite width correction factor was taken from Brown and Srawley [8].

Fig. 1. Crack opening displacement at one of the notches of the DEN specimens.

$$Y = 1.12 + 0.2(2 a/W) - 1.20(2 a/W)^2 + 1.93(2 a/W)^3 \quad (6)$$

The resulting toughness K_0 for the different notch lengths is represented in Fig. 2. The fracture toughness at maximum load K_{max} , calculated from Eq. (1) with the original notch length is also indicated in Fig. 2. It shows that K_0 as well as K_{max} increase with increasing notch length. The same observation can be made for the angle plies 90/0/90/0/90 and (+45/0/-45)_s as indicated in Fig. 3.

This dependency on the notch length leads to the conclusion that K_0 and K_{max} are no material constants. As discussed in section 1 a toughness based on the point and average stress criterion does show a dependency on the notch length. For determination of e.g. the toughness K_0 (P.S.C.) the unnotched tensile strength and the characteristic length d_0 are needed. The unnotched tensile strengths are indicated in Table 1. As the beginning of crack extension takes place through fracture of fibers which are lying directly at the notch tip, the characteristic length d_0 over which the stress is higher than the unnotched tensile strength $\sigma(r) \geq \sigma_U$ is taken to be the fiber distance which measures 0.18 mm for the (0)₅ laminate and 0.13 mm for both angle plies. For all investigated materials the increase in K_0 (P.S.C.) with notch length is very small, much smaller than the increase in the experimental values (Fig. 2 and 3). The absolute value of the toughness K_0 (P.S.C.) is in all cases at the low side. This can be attributed to:

1. The stress distribution is not given by Eq. (2); this will be discussed below.
2. The model assumes that crack extension occurs when in the first row of fibers at the notch the unnotched tensile strength σ_U is reached. Actually, the fracture stress locally restricted to the first undamaged fibers near the notch tip can deviate from an unnotched tensile strength σ_U measured on a specimen containing many fibers which can break over the complete specimen length. The determination of the real fracture stress at the notch tip should be approached statistically based on single fiber strength. For this reason no definite conclusion can be drawn for the absolute value of K_0 (P.S.C.) relative to the experimental values.

Fig. 2. The dependence of the toughness K_0 , K_{max} and K_0 (P.S.C.) on the notch length a for the unidirectional material.

Fig. 3. The dependence of the toughness K_0 , K_{max} and K_0 (P.S.C.) on the notch length a for the investigated angle plies (DEN, $2a/W = 0.5$).

An estimation of the characteristic length d_0 , based on the toughness K_{I0} of the specimens with a notch length of $a = 5$ mm, results in a characteristic length d_0 which measures 2-3 fiber distances (Fig. 2 and 3). The toughness K_{I0} (P.S.C.), calculated with these larger characteristic lengths d_0 shows an increased dependency with the notch length. However, the toughness K_{I0} at the largest notch length is not yet reached. This leads to the conclusion that the characteristic length d_0 is notch length dependent. The dependency of the characteristic dimensions on the flaw length was shown before by e.g. Prabhakaran [9], who investigated the hole size effect in bidirectional glass-epoxy.

3.2 The Influence of Matrix Splitting

It was observed that at increasing notch length the unidirectional B-SiC/Al shows a tendency to matrix splitting starting from the notch tip parallel to the fibers. This is obvious, as the load-COD curves (Fig. 1) show a steadily increasing COD with increasing notch length, which is mainly caused by an extending shear zone at the notch tip. This demonstrates Fig. 4, where for a number of notch lengths the crack opening at the tip COTD, measured from the moiré photographs, is represented as a function of the stress. The COTD measured two fiber distances away from the notch tip in the direction of the specimen side is calculated from the displacements of the fringes which are running just above and below the notch. Except for the longest notch length the displacements COTD at both notch tips (connected by a horizontal) are represented. At increasing notch length COTD becomes more and more non-linear as a result of the extending plastic shear zone.

Fig. 4. The applied stress-COTD curves at different notch lengths taken from the moiré pictures two fiber distances behind the notch tip.

The shear deformation and crack extension at the notch tip of two specimens with a higher notch length shortly before specimen fracture are shown in Fig. 5. The moiré pictures indicate extensive matrix splitting in some places.

Fig. 5. Moiré pictures showing shear deformation and crack extension at two different notch lengths (DEN) at 97 % of the fracture load.

The question arises whether and to what degree splitting causes toughness increase. This was investigated on 20 mm wide specimens, which were cut out of the rest pieces of the two widest specimens. After introducing edge notches with a length of $a = 5$ mm a cycling load (frequency 0.1-1 Hz) at about half the anticipated load at the beginning of crack extension was applied. Cyclic loading was interrupted when matrix cracks over a certain length parallel to the fibers were found. After that the fracture toughness K_0 and K_{max} were determined, in order to reveal the dependency between the toughness and the length of matrix splitting. The results are graphically represented in Fig. 6. The results of three specimens without matrix cracks are presented as if a matrix crack of $d = 0.35$ mm was present, which is the mean value of the notch depth. These are the results of the virgin material of a specimen preloaded once and of a specimen loaded 20 cycles.

The small differences between the toughness of these three specimens show that preloading and a small number of fatigue cycles do not have a considerable influence. The mean toughness K_0 for these specimens is $K_0 = 47.4 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$. The toughness rises with increasing matrix crack length up to a matrix crack length of about 4 mm. Then the toughness levels off at about $K_0 = 58.0 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$, which means an increase of 22 % compared to the specimens without matrix cracks.

Thus the toughness increase with rising notch length (Fig. 2) can partly be explained by the formation of matrix cracks at the notch tip parallel to the fibers. Splitting, however, is not so severe, certainly not at the beginning of crack extension, so that the above-mentioned maximum increase at fatigue-induced matrix cracks will not be reached. That is why there must exist other effects, which cause a rising toughness with increasing notch length. This is concluded, too, when the rising toughness for an increasing notch length for the angle plies is considered. In these materials load transfer near the notch tip takes partly place through interlaminar shear stresses. For this reason notch blunting by matrix cracking parallel to the fibers in loading direction does not occur in the same range of

Fig. 6. The toughness of unidirectional B-SiC/Al in dependency on fatigue induced matrix cracks (DEN specimens, $W = 20$, $a = 5$ mm).

notch lengths as investigated on the unidirectional material.

3.3 The Stress Distribution at the Notch Tip

It has been discussed before that in the unidirectional material the plastic zone extends more and more in the fiber direction at increasing notch length. This means that at increasing notch length load transfer takes place at an increasing distance from the notch plane. This is likely to influence the stress distribution at the notch tip.

To prove this, the strain distribution was measured on two DEN specimens with a different notch length, namely $a = 18.5$ mm (specimen width $W = 74$ mm) and $a = 4.66$ mm ($W = 19.7$ mm). The latter specimen was cut out of the former after completion of the fracture mechanics test. The strain distribution was measured with a strain gage chain, with 10 separate strain gages lying 1 mm apart. One additional strain gage in the chain, meant to be used for temperature compensation, was employed, too, for strain measurements on the 74 mm wide specimen. Temperature compensation was not necessary because of the short time in which the test was performed. The strain of each strain gage was recorded as a function of the load and later transferred into stresses by the aid of a stress-strain curve. For the wider notch length a virgin stress strain curve was used, while for the specimen cut from the preloaded material use was made of a stress-strain curve measured on a specimen out of the same pre-loaded material. The strain gages closest to the notch tip do not represent the strain of its geometrical center, due to the strongly increasing slope of the strain in this range. The effective distance from the notch tip has been estimated assuming the strain to be proportional to $1/\sqrt{r}$.

The measured stresses are compared with the theoretical values following from LEFM (Eq. (3)) and the stress distribution used for the point and average stress criterion (Eq. (2)). All stresses at the notch tip, experimental as well as theoretical, are nondimensionalized by dividing them by the applied stress σ . The experimental stress distribution at two stress levels was evaluated; first at low load, where mainly an elastic deformation takes place and second at the beginning of crack extension. The stress distribution at one of the notches in Fig. 7 shows a clear change between the load levels $\sigma/\sigma_0 = 0.14$ and the load level at the beginning of crack extension $\sigma/\sigma_0 = 1$. At the higher load level the normalized stresses close to the notch tip are lower, whereas further from the notch tip the normalized stresses are higher than the stresses for an applied load in the elastic range. This indicates that through load transfer far from the notch plane the stress distribution in the notch plane becomes more homogeneous. Thus an extending plastic zone in the direction of the load causes a diminishing stress concentration directly at the notch tip. At the notch tips no considerable matrix splitting was found in the moiré pictures, although at a smaller notch length matrix cracking actually occurred (Fig. 5, $a = 14$ mm).

The stresses measured at both notches $a = 4.66$ mm of the smaller specimen are presented in Fig. 8. The strain gages of the left notch are indicated with open, the strain gages of the right notch with filled symbols. In spite of the fact that at a notch length $a = 4.66$ mm the extension of the plastic zone in loading direction is smaller than that for the former specimen with $a = 18.5$ mm, here again occurs a clear stress redistribution at increasing load. $\sigma(r)/\sigma$ close to the notch tip decreases, whereas in the specimen center $\sigma(r)/\sigma$ rises at increasing stress. The expectation that for a smaller plastic zone the stress decrease close to the notch tip is smaller cannot be confirmed comparing Fig. 7 with Fig. 8.

What is lacking is the knowledge about the stress very close to the notch tip in the range $r = 0-0.5$ mm. We know that at the beginning of crack extension some fibers at the notch tip are breaking. If we assume that in the fibers close to the notch tip there is no stress gradient in the plane of the notch, the beginning of crack extension takes place when the stress at one fiber distance from the notch at $r = 0.18$ mm reaches the fracture stress. This fracture stress is not necessarily equal to the unnotched tensile strength σ_U , which is caused by scatter and a length dependency of the fiber strength. Short fibers usually break at a higher stress than long fibers do. For this reason a fiber at the notch tip will generally break at a higher stress than the fiber strength measured on long fibers. As the fiber strength is unknown it has been tried to estimate the stress range wherein fiber fracture can occur. The unnotched tensile strength σ_U is an indication for the fiber strength. As fracture of well-bonded undegraded boron fibers in aluminum is governed by the low-strength fiber [10] the unnotched tensile strength reflects a lower bound for the fiber strength. The unnotched tensile strength can therefore be estimated as a lower bound for the stress at $r = 0.18$ when crack extension begins. An upper bound is taken from [11], where fiber strength and specimen strength were determined on the same material (B-SiC/Al) fabricated by the same producer. The specimen strength was about the same ($\sigma_U = 1130$ N/mm²) at fiber strengths between 2300 and 3100 N/mm². From the maximum fiber strength we roughly calculate an upper stress for the beginning of crack extension with $\sigma(r = 0.18) = V_f \cdot \sigma_{f, \max} = 1674$ N/mm². The lower and upper fracture stresses are indicated in Fig. 7 and 8 at a distance $r = 0.18$ mm from the notch tip. What is the most likely fracture stress in this range? When in Fig. 7 the strain gage results at crack extension are extrapolated in the direction of the notch tip, we see that at crack extension the stress at $r = 0.18$ mm is near the maximum of the fracture stress range. As a consequence, the stress in the 19.7 mm wide specimen (Fig. 8) would rise very steep close to the notch tip. The slope of the stress distribution after Eq. (3) will, however, probably not be exceeded so that rather crack extension in the lower range of the possible fracture stress occurs. Consequently, the slope of the stress distribution close to the notch tip in Fig. 7 would decrease considerably.

This lagging stress distribution directly at the crack tip was calculated before by Tirosh [12]. He estimated the stress distribution at the tip of a sharp crack in dependency of the crack tip opening which is a result of plastic shear deformation parallel to the fibers. Neglecting the influence of the elastic shear zone, he found

Fig. 7. The experimental (at two load levels) and theoretical stress distribution at the tip of a notch $a = 18.5 \text{ mm}$ long ($W = 74 \text{ mm}$, $(O)_5$ B-SiC/A1)

Fig. 8. The experimental (at two load levels) and theoretical stress distribution at the tip of edge notches $a = 4.66 \text{ mm}$ long ($W = 19.7 \text{ mm}$, $(O)_5$ B-SiC/A1)

that directly at the crack tip there is a zone of constant stress with a length of about the crack tip opening, whereas further from the crack tip the stress distribution is proportional to $\ln(1/r)$, which is less steep than the distribution given by Eq. (3). In the present investigation the crack tip opening at the beginning of crack extension measures not more than half the fiber distance (Fig. 4), so that a stress reduction must take place beyond the COTD-value as suggested by Tirosh for a sharp crack.

Although the stress distributions at the notch tip in the angle ply material are very complicated through existing interlaminar shear stresses, an increasing notch length seems to have the same effect as in unidirectional B/AI, namely a stress redistribution at the notch tip.

The low toughness K_0 and K_{max} at the smaller notch lengths $a \leq 5$ mm (Fig. 2) is partly caused by specimen size effects. In these cases the ligament length of $W-2a = 5$ and 10 mm is too small. This is shown by the stress distribution in Fig. 8, where the normalized stresses in the specimen middle at the beginning of crack extension increase more than those in the wider specimen (Fig. 7). In the smaller specimens the distance between the notch tips is so small that the stress concentration caused by one of the notches is not yet damped at the other notch tip. This contributes to the low toughness K_0 and K_{max} of the smaller specimens.

4. CONCLUSION

1. All investigated materials showed a rising toughness at the beginning of crack extension K_0 and at fracture K_{max} with increasing notch length. A decisive role in the toughness increase of the unidirectional material is played by the plastic zone, which at increasing notch length extends more and more in the loading direction. This causes in the notch plane a stress redistribution with lower non-dimensionalized stresses at the crack tip and higher non-dimensionalized stresses in the specimen center. An expected difference in the stress redistribution at the two notch lengths of $a = 18.5$ mm and $a = 4.66$ mm could, however, not be found. Completing the stress distribution at the beginning of crack extension with a possible range of fracture stress at one fiber distance $r = 0.18$ mm from the notch tip it could be concluded that the increase in toughness at a rising notch length is caused by
 - a. the lagging stress immediately at the notch tip of larger notches, which does not occur to the same extent at smaller notches.A further toughness increase is the result of
 - b. matrix splitting, when at increasing notch length the ultimate shear deformation is exceeded,
 - c. specimen size effects in the range of the width $W \leq 20$ mm ($2a/W = 0.5$). In these cases the ligament length is too small. The notch tip stresses are interfering, causing a too small toughness K_0 and K_{max} .
2. A prediction of the toughness at the beginning of crack extension with the aid of the point stress criterion K_0 (P.S.C.) using the smallest possible characteristic length $d_0 = 0.18$ and 0.13 mm for the unidirectional material and angle plies, respectively, leads to a too low toughness and only a very small dependency with the notch length. This dependency is so small, because the criterion is based upon a fixed stress distribution at the crack tip given by Eq. (2). The absolute value of K_0 (P.S.C.) is lower than the experimental results, because
 - a. the stresses close to the notch tip are diminished due to the above-mentioned stress redistribution and the lagging tensile stress directly at the notch tip,
 - b. locally at the notch tip the fracture stress can be higher than the unnotched tensile strength σ_u determined on 10 mm wide specimens.

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